

One Unified Model of Materials, Energies and Information on Traditional Chinese Medicine

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Abstract

Background: Traditional Chinese medicine (TCM) has unique theoretical systems and correspondingly characteristic therapies. However, the unique theoretical systems encounter many difficulties in the propagation of TCM in other countries. To dissolve these difficulties, many researchers have found some ways from different viewpoints.

Method: Based on the research to dissolve these difficulties, one unified model of materials, energies and information (UMMEI) on TCM is presented.

Discussions: In the model of UMMEI on TCM, one healthy person is a complex giant system in which the materials are fundamental, the energies are powerful, and the information is connecting. The system is unified with moving materials, translating energies, and controlling information. Jing, Blood, Jin, Ye, Zang organs, Fu organs, Xingt, and Guanqiao in TCM are substantive materials. Qi in TCM is insubstantial materials, has energy and can be carriers of information. The whole body are composed of five Zang organs, six Fu organs, Xingt, and Guanqiao. The mind in TCM is the life information of one person. The body and mind of one person is a whole in TCM unified with materials, energies, and information, just like one normal working mobile phone unified with the hardware, the power supply, and the software. The mechanisms of representatives of TCM therapies and mechanisms of curing a large kind of diseases based on the unified model are presented. Some other discussions on the model are also given.

Introduction

Traditional Chinese medicine (TCM) has been a history for thousands of years, is an important part of excellent Chinese cultures, has contributed to Chinese health promotion and treatment of illnesses, and still continues to do so [1-3]. More and more persons have been benefited from TCM with the propagation of it in other countries [1, 4-6]. TCM has unique theoretical systems the theories of prenatal Qi concerned with the materiality of the world, of Yin-Yang, and of Five Elements, are the philosophical basis of TCM; holism is a characteristic of TCM in general and the theoretical cores are Zang Fu organs, meridians and collaterals, Qi and Blood and body fluids; meridians and collaterals are pathways in which the Qi and Blood of the human body circulate; the Zang Fu organs and the human body from the interior to the exterior are linked into an organic whole through meridians and collaterals; Jing, Qi, Blood, Jin, Ye are the fundamental ingredients on which

the life depends; the whole body are composed of five Zang organs (the heart, the lungs, the spleen, the liver, the kidneys), six Fu organs (the gallbladder, the stomach, the small intestine, the large intestine, the bladder, the triple burner), Xingt (the tendon, the arteries and veins, the muscles, the skin, the bones), and Guanqiao (the eyes, the tongue, the mouth, the noses, the ears, the external genitalia, the anus); the five Zang organs are the centers of the whole body; the five Zang organs are five physiological systems together with six Fu organs, Xingt, and Guanqiao through the connections of meridians and collaterals; the five Zang organs is a whole; the mind is governor and general mark of living activities including consciousness and thoughts; the body and mind of one person is a whole also [1, 7-8]. Medical herbs, a cupuncture, medical massage, and medical Qigong are four representative modes of therapy in TCM [1, 9-11]. Herbs mode is also called a medical formulation or prescription containing

More Information

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several herbs usually, for a better result is obtained than by using just one herb in most cases [1]. Acupuncture, one important green and side effect-free therapy, is widely used in a wide range of conditions, including but not limited to chronic pain, nausea, certain neurological and other diseases [12-15]. Medical massage, the other important green and side effect-free therapy, has unique effects on musculoskeletal disorders, neuropsychiatric disorders, cardiovascular disorders and many other diseases [16-18]. Medical Qigong, is also one natural, green and side effect-free therapy, which is beneficial in the helping to heal cancers, fatigues, Parkinson's diseases, stroke, Traumatic brain injury (TBI), HIV, diseases on COVID-19's, drug addiction, pains and so on [10-11, 19-26]. TCM has its unique theoretical systems and accordingly has its special therapies. However, the unique theoretical systems encounter many difficulties in the propagation of TCM in other countries for hard understanding and acceptance of the theories [1, 27-29]. To dissolve these difficulties, many researchers have found some ways from different viewpoints, such as viewpoints of philosophy [30], mathematical model based on electromagnetic radiation within the human body [31], network medicine [28, 32], systems theory [33], comparison of the history and the present situation between TCM and modern medicine [1, 34], and so on. As well known, the base of TCM and modern medicine is all life science, and fundamental activities of life is physical. Therefore, TCM can be understood and accepted from the viewpoint of physics. However, to our knowledge, the research to discuss TCM from the viewpoint of combination of material, energy, and information, has not been found. Here, one UMMEI on TCM is given. The unique theories of TCM and the mechanisms of four representative modes of therapy in TCM are explained with the model. The benefits of the model in practices of TCM are presented also.

Method

One UMMEI on traditional Chinese medicine
In the words of modern sciences, one healthy person is a complex giant system in which the materials are fundamental, the energies are powerful, and the information is connecting. The system is unified with moving materials, translating energies, and controlling information. One healthy person will be unhealthy when anyone's normal course of the three in the system is blocked.

Jing, Blood, Jin, Ye, Zang organs, Fu organs, Xingti, and Guanqiao in TCM are substantive materials. Qi in TCM is insubstantial materials, has energies and can be carriers of information. Qi is just like the electromagnetic waves used by mobile phone to communicate, one kind of insubstantial materials, not being seen and touched, however having energy and being carriers of information. In other words, Qi in TCM

has the characters of materials, energies and information which are very familiar in modern sciences. These three characters of Qi can be seen as only one or two, or three in different cases. For example, the Qi in the four kinds of basic movements of ascending, descending, leaving and entering [7] can be seen only as materials; the Qi in which Qi is considered to be the leader of Blood, and Blood is the mother of it [7] can be seen as not only materials but also energies; the Qi in the uses of which meridians and collaterals are circulating Qi and Blood, balancing Yin and Yang, sending needling sensations and adjusting deficiency and excess conditions [7] have all the three characters. Meridians and collaterals are pathways in which the Qi and Blood of the human body circulate, Blood is substantive materials, and Qi has the character of materials, energies and information, so meridians and collaterals are materials, are energies and also channels of transmitting information. The mind in TCM is the life information of one person. The substantive materials and meridians and collaterals constitute one human body, Qi is carrier of mind or life information and is full of one's whole body, so the body and mind of one person is a whole in TCM, and is unified with materials, energies, and information, just like one normal working mobile phone unified with the hardware, the power supply, and the software. The essence of therapies in TCM is to move the blocks in the course of moving materials, translating energies, and controlling information in the giant system of one patient, through all kinds of herbs, acupuncture, medical massage, and medical Qigong. By doing so, the patient can be healthy again.

In TCM one healthy person is considered as not only a whole of body and mind but also one unity of nature and the person [30], and one person is one complex open giant system [33], therefore, the movements of materials in the UMMEI can be divided into two parts in general, one is the exchange of them between the exterior and the interior of one's body, in other words, the input of nutrition and the output of waste are all normal; and the other is the generation, the interaction and the translation of Jing, Qi, Blood, Jin and Ye are normal. For the Jing, Qi, Blood, Jin, Ye, and Zang organs, Fu organs, Xingti, Guanqiao are a whole, the movements of Jing, Qi, Blood, Jin, Ye are normal, the functions of Zang organs, Fu organs, Xingti, Guanqiao are normal. Conversely, the functions of Zang organs, Fu organs, Xingti, Guanqiao are normal, and the movements of Jing, Qi, Blood, Jin, Ye are also normal. In the UMMEI, Qi is considered as insubstantial materials, energies and carriers of information, therefore, the transformations and followings of energies and controlling of information are divided into two parts in general. One is the exchanges of the energies and information or Qi between the body and the outer

environments are normal. One person reacts appropriately when the outer information transmits into the body, and the inner information can be transmitted to any part of the whole body, in other words, the following of energies and the exchanges of information have to be normal under the control of mind. That one person can dress appropriately according to the weather is an example in this part. The other is the realization of the control of mind of life information through the transmit of Qi, just like the information of talk in one normal working mobile phone is transmitted through electromagnetic waves not seen and not touched. Meridians and collaterals are pathways in which the Qi and Blood of the human body circulate [7], therefore, the means of a whole in TCM unified with materials, energies, and information are that the communicating, the controlling and all the other functions of meridians and collaterals are normal. Though one healthy person is one open system, very giant and complex, only two parts of materials constitute the person. One part is Qi which is insubstantial materials, and the other is substantive materials. The part of substantive materials is different in classifications and names between TCM and modern medicines, however, the meanings of substantive materials in the two medical systems are the same in general.

The excess or deficiencies, or disorders of movements and transformations of substantive materials and Qi in one's body, the abnormal of interactions between substantive materials and Qi, can all make one person unhealthy. For Qi is considered to be the leader of Blood, and Blood is the mother of it [7], the relationship between Qi and blood, is just like electromagnetic waves and electronic currents. The abnormal interactions between Qi, the insubstantial material, and Blood, one substantive material, are just like electromagnetic waves and electronic currents in one mobile phone are wrong. The wrong of electronic currents can make the generation of electromagnetic waves wrong, and in turn, the wrong of electromagnetic waves can destroy the normal movement of electronic currents. So, the mobile phone can not work normally. For the functions of mind of one person are just like the use of controlling software in one mobile phone, the abnormal of mind or the control of information can also make one person unhealthy, just like the wrong of controlling software can make one mobile phone work abnormally. This is pathogenesis of TCM based on the UMMEI.

The mechanisms of therapies of TCM based on the UMMEI

The mechanism of herbs of TCM is to decrease the excessive substantive materials or increase the deficient in the body of one patient. The herbs as substantive materials can correct the disorder of

movements and transformations of substantive materials in one patient through the physical, chemical and biological interactions between herbs and other substantive materials. Through these interactions, the abnormality of substantive materials in the body of one patient can be dissolved. The mechanism of mechanical acupuncture is to influence the movements of substantive materials through mechanical force, and the mechanism of electroacupuncture is to influence the movements of substantive materials through force of electronic field. The mechanism of medical massage is to influence the movements of substantive materials through mechanical force. These mechanisms are seen as only adjusting the substantive materials not involving the Qi, however, the adjusting of substantive materials inevitably can adjust the insubstantial materials or the Qi. For Qi is considered to be the leader of Blood, and Blood is the mother of it [7], all activities in the body of one patient depend on Blood directly or indirectly. In other words, the adjusting of insubstantial materials or Qi is indirectly done well. This is just like once electronic currents are adjusted well in one mobile phone, electromagnetic waves transmitted by the phone are normal.

The basic operations of medical Qigong are adjustment of body, adjustment of breathing, and adjustment of mind [11]. Adjustment of body is the mechanical movement of body, adjustment of breathing is also the mechanical movement of body in most cases, so there are some same mechanisms between medical Qigong and mechanical acupuncture or medical massage, that is to say, they are all influencing the movement of substantive materials in the body of one patient in some cases. For the Qi (insubstantial materials) is the carrier of information, the mechanism of adjustment of mind is adjusting Qi directly and adjusting substantive materials indirectly through adjusting Qi. The direct mechanism of adjustments of body and breathing are influencing the movements of substantive materials through mechanical force. The direct mechanism of adjustment of mind is influencing the movements of Qi through controlling information or mind. In the adjustments of body, breathing and mind, the adjustment of mind is the most important in Qigong practice [11]. In the course of Qigong therapies, the adjustment of mind is also a leader. For materials, energies and information all can be adjusted based on the unified model of materials, energies and information, anyone of the three can be adjusted when they are suitable for the cases in the medical practices of TCM. In the Qigong therapies, all kinds of information of adjustment of mind with Qi (insubstantial materials, carrier of energies and information) can reach any part of one patient's body, clean the blocks of materials and energies, and make the channels of controlling information communicate well. Through

these courses, one patient can get healthy. For meridians and collaterals are the channels of circulating Qi and Blood, and the channels sending information, making the channels of controlling information communicating well also means the functions of meridians and collaterals are normal. In the Qigong therapies, the function of controlling information in the UMMEI is used best. During the external Qigong therapies [11], the patient can get good benefits only by obeying the orders of the Qigong master, letting the orders into his or her mind, and following the rhythm and requirement basically. If one patient can't let the orders into his or her mind well, the effects will not be perfect. In the internal Qigong therapies [11], it is not necessary for the patient to comply with the Qigong teacher immediately, however, it has to be done for the patient to let the requirements into his or her mind and control body and mind. Only through these courses, after a certain time, the good benefits and the unity with moving materials, translating energies, and controlling information can be gotten.

The values of the UMMEI in the applications of TCM Meridians and collaterals are pathways in which the Qi and Blood of the human body circulate [7], Qi and Blood are together, however, it does not mean there is no Qi where there is no Blood. The Qi travelling inside the vessels is Ying Qi or nutrient Qi and the Qi travelling outside the vessels is Wei Qi or defensive Qi [7]. So Qi is full of the whole body of one person. Based on the UMMEI, meridians and collaterals is channel of moving materials, sending energies and communicating information, and is the only channel. Once Qi and blood is full of meridians and collaterals completely and travels freely in one's whole body, the person will be healthy.

Medical herbs can start to be effective only it is into meridians and collaterals. After herbs is into meridians and collaterals, under the effect of combined herbs and other materials and energies in it and based on the UMMEI, the Qi and blood of it are full and travelling freely, and one patient can get healthy. The characteristics of medical herbs:four properties, five flavors, a direction tendency(rising, floating, sinking and falling), and meridian tropism [35] are the forms of the application of the unified and coordinated actions of materials, energies and information in the herbs therapies. It is a good promotion for communicating TCM and modern medicines that the characteristics of medical herbs are connected with the materials, energies, and information here.

In pure acupuncture or medical massage therapies, there is no herbs into meridians and collaterals. In these cases, meridians and collaterals are acted only by mechanical force (as to mechanical acupuncture or massage) or electronic field force (as to electroacupuncture). In these cases, mechanical force

or electronic field force firstly moves the materials in meridians and collaterals, and then the Qi and Blood in it are full and circulate freely, under the effect of the unity with moving materials, translating energies, and controlling information, and finally one patient can get healthy. It is the form of the effect of the unity with moving materials, translating energies, and controlling information, that some certain meridians or collaterals or special acupoints have to be used [14, 36] for one patient to be cured in acupuncture or massage therapies. It is also a good promotion for communicating TCM and modern medicines that the characteristics of meridians and collaterals and acupoints are connected with the materials, energies, and information here.

In adjustments of body and breathing in Qigong therapies, it is the mechanical action that firstly moves the materials in meridians and collaterals. In adjustment of mind, it is the Qi (insubstantial materials, carrier of energies and information) that acts the materials in meridians and collaterals. In each of the adjustments of body, of breathing or mind, the effect of the unity with moving materials, translating energies, and controlling information is all necessary, and can not be dismissed. One patient can get the Qi and Blood in the whole body full and circulating freely, in other words, the patient can get healthy through the courses. In Qigong therapies, adjustment of mind is the most important, and different qigong forms are selected by TCM syndrome differentiation [11]; these are forms of the effect of the unity with moving materials, translating energies, and controlling information. It is also a good promotion for communicating TCM and modern medicines that the characteristics of Qigong forms are connected with the materials, energies, and information here.

The most important application of the UMMEI is the direction in Qigong therapies. Based on the knowledge of the authors, almost all clinical departments of TCM hospitals in China can prescribe herbs including the departments of acupuncture and massage. Almost each of all TCM hospitals have some departments on acupuncture and massage therapies. However, there are only a few of clinical departments on Qigong therapies in the whole country's TCM hospital. That is to say, the status is that medical herbs therapies is the most popular, the second is acupuncture and massage, and Qigong therapies is the last one and very poor one, though, they have the same therapeutic mechanisms based on the TCM theory and the UMMEI. In Qigong therapies, adjustment of mind is the most important [11]. Based on the UMMEI, moving materials, translating energies, and controlling information are a unity, one patient all can get healthy from materials moving or from energies translating or from information controlling. Qigong therapies is from

information controlling in appearance, and medical herbs therapies is from materials moving in appearance. They are equivalent in the mechanism and effect in fact in their according clinical indications. After the general public knows this, the Qigong therapies will be more and more popular.

Discussions

In TCM, meridians and collaterals are pathways in which the Qi and Blood of the human body circulate [7]. Based on the UMMEI, meridians and collaterals are the only channel of moving materials, sending energies and communicating information. In modern medicines, cardiovascular system is the channel carrying the blood and energy, and lymphatic system is connecting closely with cardiovascular system, and nervous system is the channel carrying the information. It may not be true that all functions of meridians and collaterals are equal to the ones of integral combination of cardiovascular system, lymphatic system and nervous system, however, it is true that all functions of the three systems are part of meridians and collaterals. The relationship between meridians and collaterals and the three systems may be discovered with the development of communication between TCM and modern medicines. For example, some part of relationship between meridians and collaterals and nervous system has been provided [37].

One human being is the sum of all life activities based on all kinds of cells. The relative stability of organic internal environments is the mark and condition of one healthy person. When the internal and external environments change, there will be a series of adjustments including the part of nervous system to keep the homeostasis. The integral unification of moving materials, translating energies, and controlling information is primary to keep the homeostasis and to adjust the deviation of it [38]. The materials of one human being are all kinds of molecules in the body, and some kinds of the molecules are the carriers of energy and information [38-39]. In the theoretical systems of TCM, the human being is the object of study, and the natural and social environments are the background of the human being, through this way it is to discover the holistic relationships between the human being and nature, the human being and society, one's mind and body, and the holistic relations among the parts of one's body. The guiding ideology is the holistic conception in TCM [30]. Based on the unified model of materials, energies and information, one person can keep healthy only under the integral unity of the three. This is consistent to the holistic concept of TCM. In TCM, substantive materials are not the carriers of energies and information, and only Qi is the carrier of energy and information. The essence of Qi has not been discovered [10], however, it is basic pathogenesis that the Qi is divided from normal state in TCM; the

abnormal state including two cases: one is the deficiency of Qi, the other is the disturbed Qi activity [7].

If the Qi and Blood in meridians and collaterals are full and travel freely, one patient can be healthy. How can this be realized? If one patient doesn't have the difficulties of sleep and food and drinking, s/he firstly has to have good sleep, food and drinking. After s/he can do this, then, chooses one or comprehensive TCM therapies to cure based on the personal constitution and under the help of TCM doctor. If one patient has the difficulties of sleep and food and drinking, however, has the convenience to get the help of one professional Chinese Qigong master or doctor, s/he firstly can choose Qigong therapies to cure the diseases of sleep, food and drinking, and then decides to do the next step that is whether to continue the Qigong therapies or to choose other therapies. For many Qigong therapies have very good effects to adjust the diseases of sleep, food and drinking [24-25], Qigong therapies are good ways through which Qi and Blood are full and circulate freely in meridians and collaterals [19]. Adjustment of Qi is the important task in Qigong therapies, and it is basic pathogenesis that the Qi is divided from normal state in TCM. Therefore when the diseases of sleep, food and drinking are being adjusted, other diseases are also being done. Based on the UMMEI, when the Qi are adjusted, the Blood are also done. Information controlling is the key and special part in Qigong therapies, and adjustment of mind is leading in the course, based on the UMMEI. For one healthy person, in TCM, the human body and mind is an organic whole, nature and man is one unity also [30]. One patient from being unhealthy to being healthy is just from the deviation of the whole and unity to it. The objectives of adjustments of body, breathing, and mind all direct to the whole and unity. The adjustment of mind is operated directly under the aim. The adjustments of body and breathing are operated indirectly under the aim. If one patient chooses the Qigong therapies and the aim is not rooted or divided by his or her mind, there are few effects definitely. Conversely, if one patient chooses the Qigong therapies and the aim is rooted and always directed by his or her mind, there are fine effects with no doubts, regardless of whether patient chooses external Qigong therapies [11] or internal Qigong therapies [11]. However, always directing the aim of the whole and unity is leading the course of Qigong therapies, and is the leader of all information, it does not mean that the aim is always at the center of the mind. When there is other aim, the aim of the whole and unity may be as the background. For example, when one patient is required to relax his or her mind and body and be quiet, she or he only pays her or his attention to relaxing and being quiet, ignoring

all other things after mastering the aim of the whole and unity as leading.

Based on the UMMEI, every chronic patient whose mental state is about normal, who has normal intelligence, and who can serve himself or herself basically, can be cured by choosing TCM therapies, such as medical herbs, acupuncture, massage, Qigong, etc., one or comprehensive. The functions of vital Qi in these patients' body are a little stronger than that of pathogenic Qi, or the strength of active factors that cure the patients are a little stronger than that of negative factors that block the patient to cure. The unity of moving materials, translating energies, and controlling information is acted, and more vital Qi are generated based on the UMMEI, until vital Qi are full of the whole body of the patient and pathogenic Qi are dismissed and the patients get healthy. It is said that one person with plentiful vital Qi won't be infected for pathogenic factors and their harmful effects can't influence her or his body [7, 11]. These are the mechanisms of curing these chronic patients through TCM therapies. For example, one patient with one certain cancer can firstly choose external Qigong therapies from which the patient can be see good effects in a little time [20] to relieve the most urgent symptom, such as pains [22, 40-41]. After the patient has the hope to cure the cancer through experience after external Qigong therapies, the second is to master the mechanisms of curing the cancer, and to have the faith to overcome the disease. The third is to continue to treat from about normal mental state to normal state. The last is to decide to choose only Qigong therapies or comprehensive TCM therapies to cure completely.

Limitations and Prospects

In medical herbs TCM therapies, for the multi-component and multi-target treatment [41], the mechanisms of the unified interactions of the biochemical molecules known and involved in the curing course remain unknown, and the mechanisms to combine the energies and information through the interactions of the molecules and to cure patients, based on the UMMEI, are also the aims of next research. In the course of acupuncture, some of the nervous nets and biochemical molecules involved in mechanical actions (mechanical acupuncture) or electronic fields actions have been discovered [37], however, the pictures of unification of materials, energies and information are unclear. The situations of the TCM massage therapies are just like the acupuncture. For the essence of Qi has not been discovered [10], and rareness of clinical departments and shortage of researches in Qigong therapies, the pictures of unification of materials, energies and information are lack. One same disease, for example, common cold, all can be cured, through Qigong

therapies, such as genuine Qi circulating method [11], or medical herbs. What are the concrete mechanisms of different therapies to cure one same disease from the viewpoint of unification of materials, energies and information? These are all objectives to explore in the future.

Summary

Based on the holistic concept of TCM, and the situations of modern researches on TCM, one model (UMMEI) to communicate with modern medicines, is given. Based on the model one healthy person is a complex giant system in which the materials are fundamental, the energies are powerful, and the information is connecting. The mechanisms of representatives of TCM therapies and mechanisms of curing a large kind of diseases based on the UMMEI are presented. Many parts of the myth of TCM can be discovered and one new bridge can be built between TCM and modern medicines through this model. Not only that, the discoveries of the specific laws potential in medical herbs, acupuncture, massage and Qigong therapies can promote the further development and application of theory and practice on TCM.

CRedit Authorship Contribution Statement

Jin-hua Ouyang: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization.

Xin Kong: Writing – review & editing.

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